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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF EFFECTS OF METHOTREXATE AND
METHYLPREDNISOLONE IN SPINAL CORD INJURY**Dr Anam Hassan Geelani¹, Dr Saira Tariq², Dr Johum Javed³¹Akhtar Saeed Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, ²Punjab Dental Hospital, ³Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Spinal cord injury (SCI) poses a serious threat to human health and typically results in incomplete or complete loss of motor and sensory function. The prevalence of SCI is relatively high.

Aims and objectives: The main objective of the study is to analyze the effects of methotrexate and methylprednisolone in spinal cord injury.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted in Akhtar Saeed teaching trust hospital, Lahore during March 2018 to July 2018. Data was collected from 50 patients who were suffering from spinal injury. The study was divided into two groups, one was control group and one who was treated with MTX.

Results: The data was collected from 50 patients of SCI. There were significant difference between control groups and treated groups. The data shows that the group of patients which was treated with MTX shows more close values to the control. But the separate effect shows somehow different values as compared to control.

Conclusion: It is concluded that MTX therapy could improve the deficiency of MP treatment alone, enhance the neuro protective effect, inhibit the activities of inflammatory cytokines, strengthen the anti-oxidative and anti-apoptotic effects and increase the clinical therapeutic effect, which could provide new strategies for the control of SCI.

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INTRODUCTION:

Spinal cord injury (SCI) poses a serious threat to human health and typically results in incomplete or complete loss of motor and sensory function. The prevalence of SCI is relatively high. Notably, the prevalence among the elderly (aged >60 years old) and the younger (aged 16–45 years old) have been estimated to be ~24 and 49%, respectively, which are primarily due to traffic collisions. Although various methods of treating SCI are currently used, these treatments are not effective since SCIs still result in substantial permanent morbidity and mortality. Therefore, it is important to develop a novel effective method of treating patients with SCI [1]. Primary injury often occurs in the spine, leading to SCI. The secondary damage includes inflammation, oxidative stress, neuronal apoptosis, intracellular and extracellular ion imbalance and a series of pathological reaction. Therefore, to avoid second injury and to promote the survival of axons and neurons, therapies aim to reduce or eliminate the destructive pathological response and to promote the regeneration, repair and functional reconstruction of nerve tissue in the chronic phase [2].

Now a days low dose methotrexate (MTX) and methylprednisolone (MP) has been used for the treatment of some inflammatory diseases such as secondary spinal cord damage [3]. Low dose MTX inhibits the proliferation of lymphocytes in any inflammatory response and also decreases the ability of leukocytes. Exact mechanism of this drug is still unknown but according to some studies it increases the adenosine accumulation at the inflammatory sites. Adenosine interacts with the receptors and decreases the inflammatory cells [4].

Aims and objectives:

The main objective of the study is to analyze the effects of methotrexate and methylprednisolone in spinal cord injury.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Akhtar Saeed teaching trust hospital, Lahore during March 2018 to July 2018. Data was collected from 50 patients who were suffering from spinal injury. The study was divided into two groups, one was control group and one who was treated with MTX.

Biochemical analysis:

For biochemical analysis 5cc blood sample was taken from vein and sample were processed with phosphate buffer saline using homogenizer. Blood was centrifuged at 3000rpm for 10 minutes and after that pallet was resuspended. Remove the pallet and again centrifuge at 3000rpm for 5 minutes. The resultant supernatant was separated and used for the measurement of MTX activity.

Statistical analysis:

The data was collected and analyzed by using the SPSS software program (21.0). All results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 50 patients of SCI. There were significant difference between control groups and treated groups. The data shows that the group of patients which was treated with MTX shows more close values to the control. But the separate effect shows somehow different values as compared to control.

Table 1: Values of mean MPO and LPO in all groups

Groups	Variab les	Maximum	Minimum	Mean \pm SD
Control	LPO	35.33	30.35	30.00 \pm 7.32
	MPO	0.01	0.00	0.00 \pm 1.57
MTX	LPO	58.63	54.30	54.30 \pm 7.46
	MPO	14.53	11.36	12.50 \pm 0.84
MTX (High dose)	LPO	35.00	33.00	32.25 \pm 11.68
	MPO	64.14	60.14	62.14 \pm 6.14

Table 2: Post-Hoc test values for all groups

No. Of observations	Study groups	Df	P-value
1	Control	3	0.018*
2	MTX	1	0.019*
3	MTX (High dose)	2	0.500

DISCUSSION:

The present study showed that the MTX significantly improved damaged motor function caused by SCI. Both compounds and MP combined with other drugs have been widely studied; however, to our knowledge, this is the first study to show motor function recovery in rats after traumatic SCI by a combination of MP and MTX at the level of the transcriptome [5]. Our study illustrates that the restorative effects of this combination therapy may be through the anti-inflammatory reaction, inhibition of oxidative stress and apoptosis and other common gene regulation pathways [6].

There are many pharmacological agents which described or considered as a potentially strong therapeutic effects for SCI. Steroids are also accepted as a best possible option for the treatment of SCI. They have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory and may be favorable in a time- and dose-dependent manner [7]. They have also anti-edema activities. Methylprednisolone (MP) acts through a variety of mechanisms to prevent the occurrence of secondary SCI and is currently the only food and drug administration-approved drug for the treatment of acute SCI [8].

Methotrexate (MTX) is a common anti-rheumatic drug that can improve the disease state and has anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects. MTX is generally used to compensate for the poor efficacy of glucocorticoid or other anti-rheumatic drugs. MTX can also be combined with hormones in early rheumatoid arthritis, so as to reduce hormone doses, thereby alleviating hormone side effects [9]. MTX can be taken long-term because of low cost, various routes of administration, steady long-term efficacy and high safety; namely, it can be taken as an anchor drug [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that MTX therapy could improve the deficiency of MP treatment alone, enhance the neuroprotective effect, inhibit the activities of inflammatory cytokines, strengthen the anti-oxidative and anti-apoptotic effects and increase the clinical therapeutic effect, which could provide new strategies for the control of SCI. However, in-depth research into

the mechanism of these therapeutic effects is required owing to the complexity and variety of the differentially expressed genes.

REFERENCES:

1. Kaynar MY, Hanci M, Kafadar A, Gümüştaş K, Belce A, Ciplak N. The effect of duration of compression on lipid peroxidation after experimental spinal cord injury. *Neurosurg Rev* 1998; 21:117-20.
2. Cronstein BN, Naime D, Ostad E. The anti-inflammatory mechanism of methotrexate. Increased adenosine release at inflamed sites diminishes leukocyte accumulation in an in vivo model of inflammation. *J Clin Invest* 1993; 92:2675-82.
3. Katchamart W, Trudeau J, Phumethum V, Bombardier C. Efficacy and toxicity of methotrexate (MTX) monotherapy versus MTX combination therapy with non-biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs in rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2009; 68:1105-12.
4. Chan ES, Cronstein BN. Molecular action of methotrexate in inflammatory diseases. *Arthritis Res* 2002; 4:266-73.
5. Brcken MB, Shepard MJ, Hellenbrand KG, methylprednisolone and neurological function 1 year after spinal cord injury. *J Neurosurg* 1985; 63:704-13.
6. Faden AI, Jacobs TP, Patrick DH, Smith MT. Megadose corticosteroid therapy following experimental traumatic spinal injury. *J Neurosurg* 1984; 60: 712-7.
7. Hall ED. The neuroprotective pharmacology of methylprednisolone. *J Neurosurg* 1992; 76: 13-22.
8. Braughler JM, Hall ED. Effects of multi-dose methylprednisolone sodium succinate administration on injured cat spinal cord neurofilament degradation and energy metabolism. *J Neurosurg* 1984; 61: 290-5.
9. Alibai E, Zand F, Rahimi A (2010) Erythropoietin plus methylprednisolone or methylprednisolone in the treatment of acute spinal cord injury: a preliminary report. *Crit Care Med* 38:U228-228.

10. Aoyama K, Matsumura N, Watabe M, Wang F, Kikuchi-Utsumi K, Nakaki T (2011) Caffeine and uric acid mediate glutathione synthesis for neuroprotection. *Neuroscience* 181:206-215.